

BARANGAY COUNCIL FOR THE PROTECTION OF CHILDREN, THEIR FOUR CORE RIGHTS AND ITS CONTRIBUTION TO BARANGAY GOOD GOVERNANCE

Marni A. Pamposa, Adonis S. Besa, Ph.D.

MPM Department, Sultan Kudarat State University, City of Tacurong/Sultan Kudarat, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The BCPC's leadership is essential to addressing child protection. The Philippines' child protection system is currently described as "top-down," with clear legislation and national policies that are inadequately implemented. (Rotche et al., 2019). This study aimed to determine the following: a) level of implementation of BCPC functionality; b) participation of Barangay Council; c) if there's significant relationship between implementation and participation; and d) issues and concern in the implementation. The statistical tools used for this study are the following: Mean and standard deviation, Pearson Correlation Coefficient, and percentile rank. BCPC fully implemented its functionality, however, 1% budget allocation of BCPC are attributively allocated to different programs for children. Barangay council's participation was often participated. No significant relationship between the level of implementation and participation, the null hypotheses was accepted. The top issue and concern is the term-based membership. The result suggests that BCPC's ability to deliver essential services may be impacted by insufficient funding. Understanding the level of participation of BC is crucial to ensuring that the fundamental rights are upheld at the local level. BCPC and BC might work together to successfully execute BCPC's functionality. Complete execution of programs for the welfare of children is impacted by the term-based membership of BCPC and BC. Moreover, with the consent of the SKSU Graduate School, the results were also presented to the different offices of the Local Government Unit of the City of Tacurong which have direct involvement in the implementation of BCPC programs namely CLGOO, CSWDO, ABC, and CPDCO.

Keywords: *Barangay Council for the Protection of Children (BCPC), Barangay Council (BC), survival, development, protection, participation*

INTRODUCTION

Protecting children from abuse, neglect, exploitation, and violence is known as child protection. It entails reacting to claims or suspicions of abuse, offering assistance and services to safeguard children, and holding those responsible for their harm accountable. Ensuring that all children are safe and free from harm or danger is the main objective of child protection. By developing procedures and policies that recognize hazards and take action before they cause harm, child protection also aims to stop future harm from occurring. According to the UN World Report on VAC (2006), approximately one billion children have experienced violence in various forms, such as bullying, emotional and sexual abuse, and exposure to violence. In the City of Tacurong, the Philippine National Police - Tacurong City recorded 18 cases of Children In Conflict with the Law and Children At Risk from 2020 to the 3rd quarter of 2023. Most involved/victims of this case are ages 10 to 17.

The City Social Welfare and Development Office of the City Government of Tacurong reported that the city scored 67.14% as per the assessment on the functionality of BCPC conducted by the Department of Interior and Local Government National Level, which indicates a mature level, which means some of the guidelines/criteria were implemented. Teenage pregnancy between 2021 and 2023 was documented by the Office of the City Health Services. Teenage pregnancy rates for the years 2021–2023 are 16 for ages 10–14 and 565 for ages 15–19. The importance of this study is to assess the level of implementation of BCPC's functionality in terms of budget allocation, policies and PPAs. Further, study will determine the level of participation of Barangay Council in terms of children's survival, development, protection, and participation. This somehow could contribute to the formulation of policies that can lead to the fulfillment of Filipino children's right. According to Roche et al. (2021) and UNICEF (2016), the child protection system in the Philippines is now characterized as "top-down," with clear legislation and national policy that is inadequately executed to the point where their "systemic" features are questioned. While social welfare infrastructure lacks capacity and technical competence, child protection coverage varies greatly regarding resources and approaches.

The role of barangay officials as custodian of children (DILG MC no. 2016-115) is an indispensable in realizing the goal for the welfare of children, thus, this study was conducted to determine the level of implementation of the BCPC in terms of budget allocation, policies, programs, projects, and activities for children, the level of participation of barangay councils in the four core rights of children in terms of survival, development, protection, and participation, to determine if there;s any significant relationship between the implementation and participation, and to find-out the top issue and concern in the implementation of BCPC functionality. With these objectives, the researcher hopes to come-up with a recommendations that would resolve issues on the recorded CICL, CAR, teenage pregnancy, and to the assessment on the functionality of the BCPC. This study was conducted in Four (4) months. Activities includes preparation

of data gathering instrument, asking permission for the conduct of the study, distribution of instrument and retrieval.

Research Questions

The study assessed the level of implementation of BCPC in terms of budget allocation, policies, and PPAs for children and the level of participation of Barangay Council in the four core rights of children, specifically on their survival, development, protection, and participation and its contribution to barangay good governance. It answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of implementation of BCPC in terms of:
 - a. budget allocation;
 - b. policies; and
 - c. programs, projects, and activities for children?
2. What is the level of participation of LGUs, particularly the barangay councils, in the four core rights of children:
 - a. survival;
 - b. development;
 - c. protection; and
 - d. participation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the implementation of BCPC in terms of budget allocation, policies, and PPAs for children and the level of participation of the barangay council in the four core rights of children, specifically on their survival, development, protection, and participation?
4. What are the issues and concerns in the implementation of BCPC functionality?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher chose the City of Tacurong for the following reasons: first, it has been determined that all 20 barangays have organized the BCPC; secondly, the Local Council for the Protection of Children conducts an annual evaluation of BCPC's operation thus data can be accessible. The study employed total enumeration (Arnab, 2017), as all respondents from the twenty (20) barangays were considered or included. Consequently, no sampling size techniques were employed in this study. It is most practical when the total population is manageable, such as a well-defined subgroup of a larger population (Lavrakas, 2008). The study had 369 respondents and was divided into two types: 223 BCPC members and 146 Barangay Council members. Members of the BCPC were chosen by the directives set forth as per DILG MC No. 2020-214.

The second set of respondents is the elected members of the barangay councils, who function as prescribed under RA 7160 or the Local Government Code of 1991. The respondents' demographic data was computed and tabulated according to the following: occupation, highest educational attainment, membership, civil status, age, and source of income. The demographic profile of the respondents was not part of the research

objectives. For an effective data collection process, the researcher used the following sequential procedures: approval of the research title. Second, the researcher asked permission to the Local Chief Executive of the City of Tacurong for the conduct of the study. Third, scheduled the distribution of the research questionnaire. Fourth, and the last step was retrieving the survey questionnaire. A researcher's self-made survey questionnaire was used as the instrument for data gathering. A closed-ended four-point Likert Scale questionnaire was used (Sullivan et al., 2013). Each part of the content was validated by a competent individuals from the heads of the following offices such as: CSWDO, CLGOO, Planning Office, GAD Focal Person of the SKSU, and a principal from a private elementary school.

Pilot testing of the questionnaire was done in the Municipality of Isulan, Sultan Kudarat. The questionnaire has three (3) criterion with with a total of 7 indicators having 5 questions for each indicators. The Mean and Standard Deviation was used to determine the level of implementation of BCPC functionality in terms of budget allocation, policies, and PPAs for children, and level of participation of barangay council in terms of survival, development, protection, and participation of children. Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to find-out if there's significant relationship between the implementation of BCPC functionality and participation of barangay council.

RESULTS

Table 1. What is the Level of Implementation of BCPC in terms of Budget Allocation, Policies, and PPAs for children?

Level of Implementation of BCPC	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Budget Allocation	3.21	Partially implemented
Policies	3.17	Partially implemented
PPAs	3.43	Fully implemented
Grand Mean	3.27	Fully implemented

BCPC fully implemented the children-related programs by establishing allocated budgets, policies, and PPAs with a grand mean of 3.27. Furthermore, the BCPC implementation in terms of PPAs demonstrates the highest indicator with a mean of 3.43, indicating full implementation; in this instance, it is true to say that PPAs on programs for pregnant and lactating mothers are carried out according to schedule. However, it is believed that only a portion of the budget allocation has been implemented (M-3.21) since it is attributively allocated to other activities/programs for children. This budget attribution was affirmed by the city planning officer of the LGU of the City Government of Tacurong and was supported by the CSWDO, CLGOO, and the ABC. The reason of this budget attribution for BCPC was due to limited budget allocated to barangays. Programs for child welfare are frequently unable to be implemented successfully due to a lack of funds (Koval

& Radchenko, 2019). The result implies that comparable issues with inadequate funding can arise for the BCPC, affecting its capacity to provide necessary services.

Table 2. What is the Level of Participation of LGUs, particularly the barangay councils, in the four core rights of children namely: survival, development, protection, and participation?

Level of Participation	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Survival	3.22	Often
Development	3.21	Often
Protection	3.06	Often
Participation	3.21	Often
Grand Mean	3.18	Often

Level of Participation of the Barangay Councils in the Four Core Rights of Children often participates in all its indicators. It would mean that the members of the Barangay Council often participates in the implementation of the programs relating for children relating to survival, development, protection, and participation, hence the four point likert scale shows always participated as the highest point. Children's rights to survival center on getting them access to necessities, including food, medical care, and housing. According to research by Presern (2013), attaining these rights requires putting population health at the forefront of governance.

Table 3. Is there a significant relationship between the implementation of BCPC in terms of budget allocation, policies, and PPAs for children and the level of participation of the barangay council in the four core rights of children, specifically on their survival, development, protection, and participation?

Sources of Variance	n	Pearson Correlation <i>r</i>	t-computed Value (2-tailed)	Decision
Implementation of BCPC and Participation of Barangay Council	146	0.13***	0.118 Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypotheses

Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.13 shows a weak or low correlation. On the other hand, no significant relationship was found on the t-computed value of 0.118. Thus, the Null hypothesis was accepted. It implies that the BCPC can work without collaborating with the Barangay Council. In addition, both the BCPC and Barangay Council can perform their respective responsibility even with less coordination with each other; it is because some of the members of the BCPC are also members of the Barangay Council. In this

case, it might negatively impact both councils since they must collaborate to implement BCPC functionality.

Table 4. What are the issues and concerns in the implementation of BCPC functionality?

Issues and Concerns	Frequency	%	Rank
Due to term-based membership in BCPC and the Barangay Council, its implementation was limited in time	259	87.20%	1
Insufficient educational background of the Barangay Council and BCPC Members	241	81.14%	2
Limited capacity of barangay officials and staff	229	77.10%	3
The orientation process to strengthen the BCPC has not been fully implemented	226	76.01%	4
Law enforcement inefficiency	226	76.10%	5

The top five issues and concerns: Due to term-based membership in BCPC and the Barangay Council, its implementation was limited in time, which are the leading issues and concerns (P= 87.20%, F=259). The implementation of programs for the welfare of children cannot be fully realized because the barangay council's term is limited to three years, as stated in the Local Government Code (letter c of Sec. 43-Chapter II). The Barangay Council and BCPC members' insufficient educational backgrounds came next (P=81.14%, F=241). According to the respondents' demographic information, most BCPC and Barangay Council members are college graduates (47.97%); the researcher does not think this was a major problem. The limited capacity of barangay officials and staff ranks third (P= 77.10%, F=229); this might be due to limited seminars and training. The orientation process to strengthen the BCPC has not been fully implemented, and law enforcement inefficiency ranks fourth (P= 76.01%, F=226). The issue with the implementation of the orientation process is due to a limited budget. The inefficiency of law enforcement is due to the limited awareness of the ordinances enacted by the city and Barangay.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

The BCPC emphasizes conducting programs for pregnant women and lactating mothers regularly as scheduled. The barangay council gives priority to the city's immunization and vaccination programs. There was no significant relationship between the implementation of BCPC functionality in terms of budget allocation, policies, and

PPAs and the participation of the Barangay Council on the four core rights of children, specifically on survival, development, protection, and participation; therefore, Null Hypotheses were accepted. Regarding the issue and concern in the implementation of BCPC functionality, term-based membership in BCPC and the Barangay Council got the top spot.

Recommendations

It was found out that BCPC's level of implementation is fully implemented in terms of budget allocation, policies, and PPAs. However, the researcher noted indicators that need to be given attention to policies, such as the formulation of the Local Investment Plan and Local Development Plan, which was partially implemented. It is recommended that the BCPC may involve children, parents, educators, barangay health workers, Tanods, and accredited PSOs in formulating such plans. It was determined that the level of participation of BLGU, particularly the barangay council, in the four core rights of children, specifically on survival, development, protection, and participation, is often participated. The researcher noted that the protection indicator, particularly raising awareness on mental health by providing parents with orientation, seminars, and training, often participated with the least mean among the indicators.

The researcher recommends that the BCPC may plan workshops to educate parents about common mental health conditions; provide training courses; and organization peer-led support groups. The level of implementation and participation was found to have no significant relationship, and the null hypothesis was accepted. Considering this, the researcher came up with the recommendations: both councils may create, carry out, and oversee child welfare initiatives; The Barangay Council may oversee resource distribution, logistical support, and widespread community involvement, while the BCPC may concentrate on particular child protection issues (such as managing abuse cases and providing services to children who are at risk); and both councils may work together to track and assess the results of child protection initiatives, the Barangay Council may examine the BCPC's feedback on the program's performance in order to make any necessary corrections and provide additional funds or assistance. The top issue and concern in implementing BCPCs' functionality is term-based membership in BCPC and the Barangay Council. the researcher recommend that the Barangay Council may pass a Resolution requesting the Congressman of the First District of Sultan Kudarat to sponsor a bill for the change of term of office of the barangay official from 1 term (equivalent to three years) to 1 term (equivalent to 5 years)

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In order to preserve the quality of the study, the respondents are assured to have the data and results of the research as part of their functions in the implementation of the BCPC. Moreover, with the consent of the Sultan Kudarat State University Graduate School, the results were also presented to the different offices of the Local Government Unit of the City of Tacurong which have direct involvement in the implementation of BCPC programs and others that are related to the welfare of children namely, City Local

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REFERENCES

- Arnab, R. (2017). Survey Sampling Theory and Applications
DILG MC No. 2016-115: Role of barangay officials as custodian of children.
<https://www.region12.dilg.gov.ph>
- DILG MC No. 2020-214: Comprehensive Guidelines in the Establishment, Strengthening, and Monitoring of the Local Council for the Protection of Children (LCPC) At All Levels and for other Purposes
- Lavrakas, P.J. (2008), Encyclopedia of Survey Research Methods. Sage Publication, Inc., Thousand Oaks.
- Presern, C.. (2013). Placing populations' health at the heart of the post-2015 agenda.. Bulletin of the World Health Organization , 91 7 , 467-7A .
<http://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.13.125146>
- Roche, S and Flynn, Catherine (2021): Local Child Protection in the Philippines: A Case Study of Actors, Processes and Key Risks for Children
- Roche, S. (2019). Childhoods in policy: A critical analysis of national child protection policy in the Philippines. Children & Society, 33(2), 95–110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12295>
- Sullivan, Gail M., & Artino, A.. (2013). Analyzing and interpreting data from likert-type scales.. Journal of Graduate Medical Education, 54, 541-2
. <http://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-5-4-18>
- UNICEF, (2016). UNICEF Annual Report 2016
- UN World Report on VAC (2006). United Nation World Report on Violence Against Children 2006